

FEDERATED DATA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE OPEN WEB SEARCH*

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Abstract

The World Wide Web, as an indispensable technological construct and infrastructure, catalyses innovation and underpins the foundation of our digital economy. It provides a comprehensive technological scaffold for a myriad of services, advancements, and enterprises, and is a pivotal data reservoir for researchers, creators, commercial entities, and the wider society. The initiative Open Web Search.eu [1], funded by the Horizon Europe programme [2], is designed to harness the untapped potential of the Web as a data repository and to construct a scalable and open *European open Web search and analysis infrastructure*. This infrastructure, in the absence of any comparable alternative, is predominantly under the dominion of a select cadre of gatekeepers who currently constitute an oligopoly, thereby monopolising search functionality and, by extension, the accessibility to information residing on the Web [3]. The pilot version is the *open web search federated data infrastructure*, the technological complexities of which we elucidate in this document, given that it represents the midpoint in the timeline of this initiative. It embodies the idea of a confluence of cloud, high-performance computing, big data, providing a foundation for the development of new search applications and the training of AI models. This manuscript elucidates the cutting-edge computational, storage, and interconnection technologies that serve as the backbone of this infrastructure and critically examines the deployment strategies employed in the integration of these technologies. In pursuit of the objective for this infrastructure to accommodate petabyte-scale operations upon the culmination of the project's timeline, we concurrently present a concise overview of the technological roadmap devised to actualise our performance benchmarks.

INTRODUCTION

The confluence of cloud computing, High Performance Computing (HPC), and big data is a crucial component of the OpenWebSearch.eu's (OWS) strategy to develop a flexible

and inclusive *European open web search data and analysis infrastructure*, which is inspired by Lewandowski's idea of an "open web index" [4] and the corresponding core principles [5]. This effort is carried out through a well-thought-out research and innovation strategy aimed at meeting the needs of diverse scientific communities and various public and private stakeholders interested in driving significant digital advancements using web data. These web data, considered big data due to their large volume, [6] are crawled and stored in a distributed manner, yet accessible within a unified view, and processed through independent serial/parallel computing tasks on the data segments. We aim to crawl 30–50 percent of publicly indexable web content within 3 years timeline of the project. Crawling operations are performed on cloud computing platforms that offer convenient access to computing resources typical of data centres. The subsequent preprocessing and indexing of these crawled data are categorised as big data processing tasks, ideally suited for execution on HPC systems. Currently, OWS is collaborating with 4 HPC partners (who also serve as cloud partners) and 1 cloud partner. Our collaborative efforts are primarily focused on establishing a scalable pipeline for crawling, preprocessing, and indexing on modern heterogeneous architectures. Additionally, we aim to provide easy access to the index and other datasets through various interfaces, which form the basis for developing search applications and training artificial intelligence models. The infrastructure is designed in a modular manner to enhance the efficiency of the pipeline and abstract users from its technical intricacies. By integrating HPC technologies with cloud computing and big data using user-friendly interfaces, we are working toward a practical solution that demonstrates the convergence of these technologies in a real-world scenario.

INFRASTRUCTURE ARCHITECTURE ELEMENTS

Figure 1 shows the structured layout of the OWS Federated Data Infrastructure (OWS-FDI), designed to oversee data aggregation, processing, indexing and distribution across

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various distributed computing and storage facilities. The architecture is divided into five clear and organised layers:

- Layer 1, enclosed in green boxes, are collectively known as *Interfaces*.
- Layer 2, represented by a purple box, is dedicated to the authentication and authorisation infrastructure, referred as *AAI layer*.
- Layer 3 encompasses the *cracking, pre-processing and index generation and the index post-processing layer*, contained within the ochre boxes.
- Layer 4, enclosed in a yellow box, comprises the *Computer Infrastructure layer*.
- *The OWS Data Distribution Layer*, visualised in a cyan box at the bottom, manages the distribution of data throughout the network.

Additionally, there is the

- *Single Sign-On (SSO)* functionality, which interfaces with most components to simplify user authentication and system entry.
- *Logging and Monitoring Service*, with the self-explanatory name.
- The two back-end elements, namely the *Crawling Queue* and *Compute workflow orchestration engine*, are explained with reference to the corresponding layers.

Figure 1: Layered Federated Data Infrastructure

A few months after the project kicked off, web crawling operations on the nascent OWS-FDI were started. As of March 2024, Table 1 provides a detailed overview of essential metrics following these operations. This table presents updated numbers, approximately one month subsequent to the exposition of a comparable table in the referenced deliverable [7].

Table 1: Crawling, Preprocessing and Indexing statistics as of March 2024

No. URLs discovered	ca. 9.8 billion
No. of web pages crawled	1.23 billion
No. of Hosts Accessed	29 million
Crawling queue data volume	4.7 TiB
WARC data volume	96 TiB
Preprocessed data volume	10 TiB
Index data volume	2.4 TiB
Logs and Metrics data volume	2.3 TiB

In this section, we will outline the service/components within each layer defined; In the subsequent section, the current status of implementation and deployment, as well as the prospective future plans for each service are described.

Single Sign On (SSO) feature via B2ACCESS

In the OWS-FDI framework, we adopted EUDAT B2ACCESS [8] for single-sign-on (SSO) capabilities, as it adheres to security standards and supports multiple authentication options such as eduGAIN [9] and ORCID [10]. This system, integral to EUDAT [11] Collaborative Data Infrastructure (EUDAT CDI [12]), operates through an OpenID Connect (OIDC [13]) server and acts as both an OpenID Provider (OP) and a connector for various Identity Providers (IdPs). The B2ACCESS proxy model translates credentials and manages trust and authorisation policies, incorporating TLS and mutual client authentication with X.509 certificates. Positioned as the main gateway to log into the federated layered data infrastructure (Figure 1), B2ACCESS is envisioned to extend its functionality to all public interfaces detailed in interfaces-section and developer-specific interfaces, such as log into individual iRODS zones [14], ensuring security and regulatory compliance throughout OWS-DDL.

Layer 1: Interfaces

OWS Engine Hub The Open Web Index (OWI) and the OpenWebSearch Engine Hub (OWSE-HUB) constitute the two main products of the OWS project. OWSE-HUB, conceptualised similar to Docker Hub [15] but for search engines, is a web-based GUI offering various search engine stacks. This setup is designed to efficiently expedite the creation of new search categories. It is configured to interface with the OWS-DDL, as depicted in Figure 1, helping to retrieve the index specifications. More details are available in the following deliverable [16].

Custom UIs This interface layer targets specialised applications, like web analytics, that use web data for various scenarios beyond simple search functions. The key to any custom user interface application is authentication, which is essential for accessing data. Data access is offered in two primary forms:

- **Download:** Users can download data sets or files organised by the HPC Workflow App for local use. This method adapts to the client’s storage technology, but limits data selection to partitions or files, requiring clients to perform further data filtering.
- **Offload:** Through OWS Observability Control App, authenticated users can set up and schedule data transfers to different storage technologies. This option allows for more extensive filtering and is more bandwidth-efficient, suitable for clients with limited storage.

The project aims to facilitate the access to data for third-party developers to create applications using these resources, enhancing the data according to their needs.

Web search applications The OWS-FDI was established to streamline the development of specialised search applications using the OWI, differing from broad search engines like Google [17] or Bing [18], which focus on general topics. This framework supports the creation of vertical search engines that offer targeted search and retrieval options. Partners working on this aim to provide guidance, technical documentation, and a prototype application [19] created to access the OWI and send queries to it through a REST API based on a modular and configurable system depending on purpose and needs; this has facilitated the development of two specific search applications [20]. This initiative is part of the broader OWS goal of fostering a network of niche search engines and related applications, with the OWS-FDI hosting and providing access to these resources.

OWS Observability and Control App This is a software tool designed for system monitoring and management, providing comprehensive analysis and operational oversight. Designed as a single-page web application [21], it uses various cloud services, with a functional summary displayed in Figure 2. It requires B2ACCESS account authentication and incorporates essential features as outlined below.

Figure 2: Observability and Control App

- **Crawling Metrics Dashboard:** Termed as the OWLer Dashboard service, it tracks and analyses metrics like crawled pages, pre-processed documents, and indexed data over various timeframes. It provides aggregated statistics for websites and hosts, in addition to live tracking of crawling activities. More information is available in the following deliverable [34].
- **Collection Index API:** Facilitates access to statistics for primary and specific subindices. Users can define collection indices and transfer data to storage systems such as OpenSearch [22], Elasticsearch [23], and S3 [24] using off-load filters.
- **Worker Components:** Executes user-defined tasks using nearby cloud infrastructure to minimise network costs. Data centres host worker groups that synchronise with the API through a REDIS [25] message queue, using a PySpark [26]-based library, the Collection Index Processor.

Interfaces to other Components

- Most functions necessitate authentication through B2ACCESS.
- An API offers programmatic access to the various functions and data elements.
- The application can access the crawling queue through the metrics server and the OWS-DDL to collect statistics and perform different operations (e.g. data offloading).

Compute workflow orchestration engine The backend of HPC Workflow App, as shown in Figure 1, optimises the HPC workflows for OWS by managing the pre-processing and indexing of the crawled data. Initially reliant on traditional batch scheduling for resource allocation, it now incorporates the compute workflow orchestration engine of the LEXIS [27] framework, addressing the diversity, scale and geographical spread of OWS-FDI [28]. This engine also interfaces with the batch scheduler and AAI for security, enhancing overall efficiency. It manages data inconsistencies via OWS-DDL and handles software provisioning, VM creation, and task distribution across the compute infrastructure (Layer 4), coordinating with HEAppE [29] middleware for secure access to HPC/cloud infrastructures.

The first paper is ready to be submitted, if you have time today, could you please skim through it? otherwise it's ok, I will go ahead and submit it.

HPC Workflow App The GUI facilitates interaction with the Compute workflow orchestration engine, enhancing workflow management by organising them as directed acyclic graphs (DAGs). It supports creating, viewing, and modifying datasets, managing metadata, and performing file operations within dataset directories. Integrated with the OWS-DDL, it improves data discoverability and replication across multiple supercomputing centres, accommodating specific requirements like GPU usage. This component is part of the LEXIS framework.

OWS Download This component, as illustrated in Figure 1, simplifies access to key datasets after preprocessing and indexing. Users can download these through HPC Workflow app. The OWS-DDL Dataset Listing [30] feature provides a summary of the datasets available in OWS-DDL, including metadata, all stored in the platform.

Layer 2: Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure Layer (AAI)

The OWS-FDI features a network of services that supports various user roles and domains, as depicted in Figure 1. These services, which include user interfaces and back-end support, such as OWS-DDL, can function independently and collaboratively. Integration with AAI, facilitated by the LEXIS framework and Keycloak [31], a single sign-on (SSO) identity and access management (IAM) solution, allows seamless access to all platform services. Keycloak integration with B2Access streamlines access, enhances security, and improves user experience. It supports OIDC,

REST interfaces and JWT tokens for service interaction, and uses role-based access control (RBAC) or attribute-based access control (ABAC). The decentralised AAI approach enhances system resilience, with HEAppE middleware acting as a crucial integration layer with local HPC centre’s AAI solutions.

Layer 3: Crawling, Pre-processing, Index generation

Crawling queue This component monitors the status and sequencing of crawled and pending URLs, access statistics, and cache digest. The Frontier queue, depicted in Figure 3, stores URLs discovered or visited during crawls. As summarised in Table 1, the crawling queue contains 4.7 TiB of stored URLs and contains a total of 9.8 billion discovered URLs.

Figure 3: Crawling Queue Service

The crawling queue consists of the following components, as depicted in Figure 3:

- *Frontier applications*, connected to the opensearch cluster, centralises and coordinates crawling priorities among data centres, using the NGI-funded URL Frontier [33], enhanced for dynamic partitioning. These applications interact with Logging and Monitoring service. For further information, consulting the following deliverable [34] is recommended.
- *The OpenSearch Cluster* serves as the back-end for the frontier apps and monitors operational metrics. OpenSearch integrates with Grafana [35] for real-time cluster status and provides dashboards for data visualisation and cluster management.

Access to these services is secured through IP addresses that are specifically whitelisted and restricted to service participants in partner computing centres.

Crawlers Figure 4 shows the components of the Crawler service. Automated crawlers collect data from the Internet, generating WARC [36] files (collections of HTTP data

streams from web crawls), stored in the OWS-DDL’s object store for shared access. [37] As summarised in Table 1, the aggregate amount of WARC data is 96TiB. This sophisticated system is based on the StormCrawler [38] platform within an Apache Storm [39] cluster. It includes three primary pipelines:

- WARC2WARC for integrating external WARC files;
- Exploratory crawling for regular web crawls; and
- Sitemap crawling, which uses the Sitemap protocol.

The crawlers operate in various data centres, communicating with the crawling queue via frontier apps and Logging and Monitoring service, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Crawlers

For additional details, it is recommended to refer to the deliverable cited [34].

Pre-processing and Index generation The pre-processing is divided into two main tasks, as depicted in Figure 5 and described below.

- *Pre-processing*: This phase focusses on enrichment and content analysis. It starts with retrieving WARC files from the local object store in OWS-DDL, populated by crawlers. The cleaned HTML and metadata are extracted from these files and stored separately within the same OWS-DDL framework. The metadata from this stage are saved in Apache Parquet [40] format.
- *Evaluation of the pre-processing plugin*: This task involves evaluating plugins for the content analysis library. These plugins, developed by project members or external contributors, enhance the enrichment process. Using Apache Spark [41] batch jobs, leveraging Resiliparse [42] to parse and clean HTML content, and implementing various metadata enrichments.

The index generation process, a continuation of pre-processing, transforms the cleaned and enriched data into a practical index, often in the form of an inverted file. This transformation involves segmenting the indexes into ‘shards’ based on specific metadata categories such as topic and language, identified during preprocessing. These shards are then formatted and distributed in the Common Index File Format (CIFF). Similarly to the pre-processing phase, index-

Figure 5: Preprocessing and Indexing

ing is executed through an Apache Spark batch operation, enabling the creation of semantically cohesive shards of the complete web index. This method leverages the metadata obtained during preprocessing to facilitate the development of specialised search engines tailored for distinct purposes like different languages, regions, or specific topics such as news and sports. For additional details, refer to the deliverable cited here [43].

As summarised in Table 1, the aggregate amount of pre-processed data is 10TiB and the size of the index is 2.4TiB.

Index post-processing (LLMs) Once the index is created, a post-processing phase is implemented, as shown in Figure 1. This stage may involve training extensive language models (LLMs) to analyse or categorise the content. These post-processing tools, developed from initial indexing results and potentially using LLMs trained on selected web content subsets, are not yet available. However, as the data become openly accessible to both the project consortium and the broader community, new applications and methodologies are expected to emerge, improving the utility of the indexed data.

Layer 4: Compute infrastructure and storage

Infrastructure providers offer vital computing and storage resources for the project, including traditional High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Infrastructure-as-a-Service cloud (IaaS-cloud) solutions. The project leverages a combination of large-scale cloud computing resources and HPCs distributed in various locations, integrated with some of the top 20 supercomputers worldwide [44]. These computing resources form the backbone of all OWS-FDI operations. As depicted in Figure 1, the HPC/Cloud infrastructure and storage layer enable the interplay between HPC and cloud systems, supplying the necessary computational strength and storage space. All facilities comply with ISO 27001 [45] standards, ensuring that IT security management is in accordance with this framework.

The confluence of Cloud and HPC in OWS-FDI Some partners provide Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) platforms featuring on-premise cloud solutions for on-

demand provisioning of high-performance virtual machines and bare metal machines. These support multiple CPU cores, RAM, and run services in different zones. The machines are equipped with HDD/SSD and scalable S3 cloud storage clusters, optimised for tasks like crawler applications via Kubernetes [46], and built on OpenStack [47] or VMWare [48]-based IaaS clouds. This setup combines cloud computing advantages with physical infrastructure control, supporting the deployment and management of scalable applications. Storage clusters, secured with TLS for API communications, are accessible through machines or containers. This cloud ecosystem complements the HPC infrastructure, merging cloud and supercomputing capabilities to efficiently manage large volumes of crawled data. Security is managed by internal teams, with access to the infrastructure restricted to specific IP addresses, which limits external access from other services or centres.

Logging and Monitoring Service

This module collects logs and metrics from all other modules and interfaces with OWS Observability and Control App, as shown in Figure 1, making public log data and metrics accessible. As summarised in Table 1, the aggregate amount of log data is 2.3 TiB. This approach improves transparency, increases community participation, and helps collaborative problem solving. Public logs are especially valuable for open source projects or public services, as they establish credibility by displaying real-time system performance and serve as an educational resource for a deeper understanding of the system. They also comply with regulatory mandates for operational transparency. Care is taken to preserve these public logs to ensure security and privacy standards.

Figure 6: Logging and Monitoring Service

In the upper layers of Figure 6, the central component is an Apache Flink [49] Cluster, a monitored data streaming platform that works in conjunction with the OpenSearch Cluster. These layers interact with OWS-DDL, granting access to logs and metrics from different components. OpenSearch dashboards [50], serving as analysis and development interfaces, provide visual representations of OpenSearch data

and aid in managing and expanding the OpenSearch cluster, benefiting both development and operational activities.

OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL)

The OWS-FDI uses a distributed architecture for data computation and storage. Figure 7 shows the distributed storage. This layer employs geodistributed storage and mirroring to ensure data redundancy and safety, although mirroring may not always be required. Using the Integrated Rule-Orientated Data System (iRODS) and EUDAT-B2SAFE, each site corresponds to an iRODS zone, illustrated in Figure 7. Data storage and management are spread across 5 participating data centres; for the sake of illustration, we have used 3 of them named A, B, and C, each equipped with local storage compatible with S3 and a corresponding iRODS zone. These zones are interconnected, facilitating data transfer and sharing. iRODS handles metadata for datasets in an iCAT [51] metadata catalogue, allowing a unified view of data across all sites. The access privileges are managed using the iRODS mechanisms, supported by AAI for SSO. This layer oversees various data sets and facilitates secure, location-independent data retrieval, and integration with other OWS-FDI components through REST APIs for data exchange. Its objective is to provide seamless cross-site access to datasets, making them available as part of a unified file system in different back-end data systems [52].

Figure 7: OWS Data Distribution Layer

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS AND ROADMAP

This segment provides a comprehensive update on the current implementation and deployment status of each specific component, together with the strategic plan established for the remaining duration of the project. Unlike the previous section, where components were categorised by layers, this section will individually discuss each component to provide a more detailed overview. Overall, all components are set up and ready for testing, which includes:

- enhancing scalability,

- extending to more data centers, and
- adding extra functions/features.

Single Sign On (SSO) feature via B2ACCESS

B2ACCESS currently serves as the login gateway for OWS Observability and Control App and operates as one of the Identity Providers (IdP) integrated into the Keycloak interface of AAI. Its integration with the iRODS zone at a partner data centre site is underway, and other sites are expected to follow suit over the next year. Furthermore, efforts to incorporate B2ACCESS for authentication between different components within interface layers, as described in previous sections and illustrated in Figure 1, will begin in the coming year.

OWS Engine Hub The OWSE-HUB initiative has begun with steps such as incorporating the indexer and the CIFF standard into TIRA [53]. This integration has provided insight on the use of pipeline indexes on a central platform, guiding future plans. Detailed plans for OWSE-HUB will be developed, focussing on defining the search engine’s formulation and presentation. The ‘hub’ will be configured to distribute these specifications, as shown in Figure 1. The aim is to launch the OWSE-HUB’s initial version by the end of the second year.

Web search applications The prototype application along with a pair of use case applications are currently housed on-site at the developer partner locations. Planning is in place for their transition to the infrastructure provided by the cloud service partners. Close work is ongoing with developer partners themselves, who have experience in search applications and user experience, to design deployment strategies that make the best use of resources. Our goal is to deploy these applications in a way that is efficient, secure, and publicly accessible, as illustrated in Figure 1.

OWS Observability and Control App This part includes the OWLER Dashboard and the Collection Index API, illustrated in Figure 2, both of which are currently in the initial development stages. The development partners aim to improve user-friendliness and collaborate with external parties to use the available data.

HPC Workflow App and Compute workflow orchestration engine The sequential processes of Preprocessing and Indexing were previously managed by a batch scheduler on different computing nodes, accessed mainly through SSH and a CLI on the front-end node of an HPC cluster. Now, as shown in Figure 2, the system is becoming automated with the HPC Workflow App as the front-end interface and the compute workflow orchestration engine as the back-end.

This transition leverages the advanced execution environment offered by HPC partners within the LEXIS framework, providing access to supercomputers and cloud resources. This integration improves the management and transfer of

Figure 8: The Lexis Platform

Figure 9: Workflow execution organized and displayed as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)

large data sets, particularly in relation to Figure 7. The HPC Workflow App initiates preprocessing and indexing tasks, triggering the respective scripts. The variety of workflows operating on the LEXIS platform is depicted in Figure 8. These processes, structured as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), are shown in Figure 9. For both workflows, an Apache Spark cluster is established in the HPC environment, and a Spark job is submitted to index the preprocessed data for a specific day (as defined in LEXIS).

The pipeline is operable through the HPC Workflow app and can interface with S3 storage. The incorporation of the LEXIS Data Staging [54] and Data Set API is being implemented. This integration is a focus, aiming to allow developers to divide tasks into executable blocks within the LEXIS framework. Plans also include monitoring distributed data and interim results through the HPC Workflow app, with B2ACCESS supporting secure authentication.

Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) Layer The LEXIS framework integrates HPC Workflow App, Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine, and OWS Download to improve user access via the AAI layer. This is depicted in the top three layers of Figure 1. Keycloak, the current AAI platform, handles the authentication process on the login page. B2Access, integrated as an IdP in Keycloak, enables users of the OWS consortium to authenticate with their institutional credentials, eliminating the need for multiple logins. Future enhancements aim to extend this access to more OWS-FDI components and OWS-DDL, further easing platform integration.

Crawling Queue The queue configuration, as shown in Figure 3, links two Frontier App instances to a separate instance that hosts a Back-End OpenSearch cluster. Logical volumes manage storage across physical hard disks. Data availability is ensured by external S3 clusters, and data in transit are protected by TLS encryption. OpenSearch oversees authentication, maintaining a database of user roles and hashed passwords. Basic-auth credentials are managed by partner sites. The current deployment is hosted on a partner cloud site, accessible via SSH.

Future plans include enhancing scalability for Frontier Apps by scaling up data nodes and incorporating a warm/hot storage mechanism. [55] Memory usage is optimised by adhering to the maximum standard limit per process. In the next stages, we plan to connect to OWS-DDL to share public logs and metrics, implement horizontal scaling for additional crawlers, and integrate with the open webmaster console [56].

Crawlers The crawlers implemented, shown in Figure 4, are integrated into the cloud infrastructure of three sites and are operational. The WARC files are stored in S3 buckets at each site for easy access by other components. Currently, crawlers are handling about 1.5TB of content daily, with plans to increase this to between 2 and 10 TB/day in the second year.

Pre-processing and Indexing Operational pipelines use the same infrastructure as crawlers, using HPC infrastructure. They align with the details in the previous section (Figure 5). Pre-processing and indexing were executed as Spark batch processes using the Magpie script collection. This method has been phased out as detailed in the HPC Workflow App and Compute Workflow Orchestration Engine sections. An instance of a TIRA platform is operational in a data centre.

Current efforts for Y2 focus on expanding the preprocessing/enrichment and indexing processes for crawled content. Functionality will be developed to estimate resources needed for processing a day’s worth of WARC files, ensuring scalability with the volume of content crawled.

The Log Aggregation and Metrics Service The cloud-based service, as shown in Figure 6, collects log files from the crawler component (Figure 4) and monitors various components. All log data and metrics are stored in OpenSearch indexes.

OpenSearch is used to manage large data sets and aggregate logs. It uses a Dockerized Flink cluster, monitored by Dockerized Grafana as shown in Figure 6. It processes crawler logs in real time, extracts, combines, and writes them back into the OpenSearch cluster.

Cron jobs populate the blacklist index and periodic snapshots of OpenSearch clusters are stored in an external S3 cluster. In the second year, the plan is to scale the OpenSearch cluster, aggregate logs from other components through OWS-DDL, and identify and address any structural bottlenecks.

OWS Data Distribution Layer (OWS-DDL)

All partner data centres have implemented iRODS, enabling OWS-DDL. They can transfer data through iRODS zones, offering various storage options, including cloud CEPH [57] storage clusters, NFS-accessible storage, and S3 storage clusters. Currently, all HPC/data centres in OWS use S3 object storage for caching, with one using it for disaster recovery.

CONCLUSION

The ambitious goal of processing 1 PB of raw web data in OWS, followed by its preprocessing and indexing for search applications, requires a sophisticated, user-friendly, and flexible infrastructure. Leveraging both cloud and HPC resources, a robust system has been developed to achieve this goal within the planned timeframe. OWS partners have effectively created and deployed a fully operational pilot Federated Data Infrastructure that supports the entire workflow from web crawling to preprocessing and indexing across various infrastructure partners. By March 20, 2024, the project had indexed approximately 1.23 billion web pages in 185 languages, utilising about 77 TiB of storage. In the project's final phase, the aim is to refine and expand the pilot OWS-FDI, extending it to additional consortium partners' sites to enhance resource utilisation. Concurrently, the performance and throughput of the existing layers depicted in Figure 1 will be assessed for scalability and potential improvements.

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